

[KbmOwācwīrēāusupmrsnāvīncsuī

armi hāmi hāqū

pmwrītuōī

[KbmOwīrēāusupmūī tv, ācwīrēāusupm [k urīhīpmynm&Sīrsm;u tpOf
tquī todtrsvīyūuavon/ oiūm;ritaxmuftujzppā&ēf&nīrēfī taxmuft
txm;rsn;uīlīcīl, kījciēnt? oīyāzmpōpēntīrsm;jzīhāvīvmclīygon/ avīvmrīt&
[KbmOwī (tv, ācwī) rēpmayā&om;rī urīhīpmtaxmuftxm;rsn;? a&xīrl
talūmīfīt&mrsm;? a&om;xm;ritajctaersn;uīlīpmayacwī trsvīvuPmwīpēntī
a, bī, sōīyībābmūīāzīyēīlīygon/ xīlūmīhītv, ācwīrēpmayā a, sōk s
ōīyībābmūīōē;vnīyī? rēpmayvīvmrī rēlōmōmpum;āvīvmrī oiūm;rES h
pmay? bōmōmpum;? , Oāusīrlōāwōēvīyīēfīrsm;uīlītaxmuftujyīrīnī [karōvīh
ygon/

aomīsupum;vīrsm;/ / pmayacwī tu&moīyī c&mōēf? rēfīyīl arēpm;
pum;vīl/

edgēf

jreīrēīlīfī h&Sā [mīf urīhīāusupmrsn;wīf [KbmOwācwī rēāusupmrsn;onīvnī
tā&ygvīygon/ yīācwīrēāusupmrsn; \āemūyīlīfwīf rēpmayātā&tom;rsn;
quīvu&āēonī [k , Mūnīrēfīqēīlīāomīvnī taxmuftxm;rsn;ESīrlīlībūīrsm;pōhīrawīl
&ay/ oīāomī [KbmOwāūmīfīpm;āom umvūīrlī rēpmayātā&tom;rsn;uīlīawīlīy
onī/ orīlīfynm&Sīwīlīāzīyīrīt& [KbmOwācwīyīct;uīlīat'D1300 rSat'D1500 cī
lūm;umv [kazīyīrēfīqīlīygon/

rēpmayacwīōwīrsvīrESī [KbmOwācwī

rēpmayacwīuīlī ovrīsvāzīyīlū&mwīf tpOf tvmt; jzīh ā&Sīrēlī acwīv, fēlī
, āēācwī rēfīlī ovrīsvājīymqīlīygon/ āusupmynm&Sī? orīlīfynm&Sīrsm;urī
rēpmayacwīuīlīacwī(6)acwīyīlīfīcm;āzīyīxm;ygon/ , īfīwīlīhī-

- 1/ ' hī&moWācwīat' (600-1000)?
- 2/ oīxīācwīat' (1000-1100)?
- 3/ yīāācwīat' (11000-1200)?
- 4/ [m&āōācwī(vēzēf) at' (1200-1300)?
- 5/ [KbmOwācwī(yīct^A*īlī^)^at' (1300-1500)?
- 6/ rsuārīhīuācwīat' (1500-1900)?

wīlījzplīygon/¹

* wīlīyīgarmū?jreīrēmpmīxme? yīct;wūīōlīvī
¹ cspīōēf? 1965? *-C/

'–at' (600-1000)rn , aeV xHfEh fi k, hjrtwUf–om avmb–
 ES hy–ow' jzplygon/ r–rm; aexH bMlyD r–may? r–, O–rl x–um;
 clygon/ xH' owUf r–mayx–um; chMumi f xH' oawU r–um–rm; u ou–o
 xlvuf –gon/ xi–rm; aom r–um–rm; tjzpf avmb– r–um–rm? y–xH
 r–um–rm' jzplygon/'² azmfyyg y–xH r–um–rm' r–rm–u–v– f–om
 tcg atmfygtwUf zv– fzw–Eh fyon/'³

'karmygp–k arm, h' –pf [mifured , f –ftMbi fumupd =	vH –M–m-' igADg–)(o–armtf –w–AmrAd[m&
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y(1)y–xH r–um–rm'

xHtwl avmb– r–um–rm' atmfygtwUf aw–Eh fyon/'

y(2) avmb– r–um–rm

azmfyyg r–um–rm' onf '–at' r–mayjzplygon/ tapmqH r–may ta&;
 tu–mo–fyiftjzpfvnt, r–v–, Eh fyon/'

ox–at' (1000-1100)rn r–may taxmuftxm;rm;t& , aeV jre–Eh fi H
 \ r–yn–, i ox–zm;t& arm–v– fi O–usi h' o [k q–ygrn/ xH' owUf '–at'

² cp–? 1965? *-C/
³ jr? 1961? aemu–u–w–, m;y–
⁴ onjrw–2015?(aemu–u–w–)q/

acwixuf aemufuom rēausupm taxmufxm; rsm; uli awfīri ae&ī jzpfygon/
 azmfy&aomf Mwmyāusupm? y@yfausupmwjzpaLumi f, azmfyxm; Muygon/ ⁵ xh
 ausupm rsm; uli , ck oxhll&pm&lb&m; ausupm/2w/f awfēh ygon/ bm; t h-ll te d
 aumuef* &f qif; wawmf wpiqN oufawmf S rēausupm ES h oxhll a&pm&lb&m; &f
 rdvhausupmwlonvnt, oxhllcwf rēausupm rsm; tjzpf xi&f; Muygon/ ⁶ xh twl
 oxhllvsm P btf rēausupm ES h ulefawm lb&m; ysuf S rēpmyg tkvfym; pmwll h vnt
 oxhllcwf a&S rēp rsm; tjzpf azmfy Muygon/ ⁷

y(3) Mwmyāusupm

y(4) y@yfausupm

oxhllcwfēhoni yk' hllcwf at' (11000-1200) umvwll vnt, rēausupm rsm;
 uli awfēygon/ xhllcwlonvnt, a&S rēausupmumv [kyif rsvf, Muygon/
 q&mbu d Opcpbe f, \ rēausupmaygif; clyft & yk' hllcwf xh rēausupm rsm; r h N* Bwd
 bDem' wvs' r® & mZibllch useppom; rif bu d \ ausupm r h trsm; p jzpaLumi f, awfēygon
 on/ ⁸ xh llēf ausupm rsm; uli yk' h' wllawf oul bll yk' h' or [kwlonh jynll-ll?
 oxhllla' owlwll vnt, awfēygon/

y(5) jynll hll a&q hllwml b&m; rēausupm

y(6) oxhllustulwv f, rēausupm ⁹

⁵ cploef? 1965? C? tyll f(1)1-7? tyll f(2)1-5/

⁶ -, if-? !? tyll f(1)9-10/ tyll f(2)6/

⁷ -, if-? tyll f(1)8-9? 10/ tyll f(2)5-6/

⁸ -, if-? 22-52/

⁹ atmi jri d? 2015? 36/

apmvtrifausupm [k xi&fi;aom jrpfom;N W ayawmausuf, ausupmonfvnf, apmvtri;vufxua&;xhaom yk' h'acwrf'eausupmwptsyfjzplygon/ ¹⁰

y(7)jrpfom;N h'ayawmausni f(apmvtri f)ausupm?

ajrmutbursuEfi-r'ebmom

&mZulm&f'eausupm \ aemuivf f yk' h'acwrf'wuf r'eausupm [k r'wif, &avmuf atmi f aemuixyrf'eausupm raw&ay/ xixuf aemuurs aw&aom r'eausupmwlr'fi q&mbu'p'ocp'of \ azmfyrft &¹¹ yk' h'acwrf [kvyl tv, h'acwrf'eausupm [k q'haom r'eausupm rsm; yifjzplygon/

[h'om'w'acwrf'eausupm rsm;

tv, h'acwrf'eausupm [k q'haom r'eausupmwll'ynm&S'wlu E'p'yl f'clum-

(1) [m&b'ocw(ve'z'ef) at' (1200-1300)? E'f h

(2) [h'om'w'acw(y'ct;^A*H^')at' (1300-1500)?

[li azmfyluygon/ tv, h'acwrf'eausupm trsm;plr'fi [h'om'w'acwrf "r'apw'rif vufxuf a&;xhaomausupm rsm; jzplygon/ xhausupm rsm;u'f, ael'wn&&m a' o tv'up'pn'fi azmfyygu atmu'fgtw'if aw'El'lygon/ atmu'fgZ, m; rsm;u'f'lyg/

¹⁰ armi'armi'haq 2014? 8/

¹¹ c'p'of? 1965? 32/

Z, m(1)

a&Sa [mi f o l w o e r S x e f o t f x m a o m [l b n O w a c w f r e a u s u p m r s n

pOf	, ae l w n a e & m	r e a u s u p m a y g i f c s y f r f n a z m j y a o m t r n f	t a l l u m i f t & m t c s y f	r s w t s u f
1	y b t f r w a & a [m i f o l w o e x m e / (a j y m i f a &)	« c s p ^ 6 5 ? 6 6 » y b t f b & m ; c E p i q l a u s u p m i , f	[l b m O w j y n & m r m " j y w d (" r a p w) r i f B u p o n f a & S t c g u w e b r i f B u D \ r e z & m ; r [m o l b ' m w n f x m ; c h o m b & m ; (7) q u l l x y f j y i f q i a l l u m i f a & ; x l l x m ; a o m a u s u p m j z p o n f /	y b t f r w t i f * s i e l) m O p u s e f x l l & o n f /
2	a & a [m i f o l w o e x m e c f (a j y m i f a &)	« c s p ^ 9 9 » y b o f r w a & l u n f a & a e m u f b & m ; a u s u p m	a p w l v p q l w e f " m v l a w m l u k w e s h a l l u ; q i f w p o n f w l u l v s ' g e f a l l u m i f a & ; x l l x m ; a o m a u s u p m j z p o n f /	y b o f r w a & l u n f a & a e m u f b & m ; t w e f O p o h a w l & o n f /
3	, H ' , m ; j y n f b e a u m u f r w t r t o m ; j y w l u f	« c s p ^ 9 7 ? 9 8 » a l l u ; j y m ; y & ; y l l u p m	a p w l v p q l w n a l l u m i f r s w l v r f w i f a & ; x l l x m ; o n f /	a t m u f j r e f m j y n f t a & y l l f w p a e & m & a p w l v p q l r s r l v a e & m j z p f [e & a o n f /

Z, m(2)

y k H ' o t w e f a w & a o m [l b n O w a c w f r e a u s u p m r s n

pOf	, ae l w n a e & m	r e a u s u p m a y g i f c s y f r f n a z m j y t r n f	t a l l u m i f t & m t c s y f	r s w t s u f
1	y k r w a & p n f c h b & m ; & i f y i a w m f (r l v a e & m)	« c s p ^ 1 0 5 » y k r w a & p n f c h b & m ; b & i h e m i f a c g i f a v m i f p m	[l b m O w r s q i j z l r s m ; & S l b & i h e m i f r i f w & m ; B u p o n f y k r w a & p n f c h b & m ; w e f a c g i f a v m i f w p l v l v s ' g e f a l l u m i f a & ; x l l x m ; o n f /	

ပုံ(၈) ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော်

၃, ၄(၃)

ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော်

ပုံစံ	အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	အကျဉ်းချုပ်
၁	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် (အကျဉ်းချုပ်)	«ဥပနိဒ္ဓိ ၆၉/၇၀/» ဝိသုဒ္ဓိ အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	
၂	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	«ဥပနိဒ္ဓိ ၇၁» ဝိသုဒ္ဓိ အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	
၃	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	«ဥပနိဒ္ဓိ ၇၂» ဝိသုဒ္ဓိ အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	
၄	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	«ဥပနိဒ္ဓိ ၇၃» ဝိသုဒ္ဓိ အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	
၅	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	«ဥပနိဒ္ဓိ ၇၄» ဝိသုဒ္ဓိ အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	ဝိသုဒ္ဓိတရားတော် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ် အကျဉ်းချုပ်	

p0f	, ae\wn&e&m	r&e&usupm aygifc&yf&f&h azmjytrnf	tallumi f t&mtc&yf	rsvtsuf
6	yct;N~W a&f&Bub&m;/ ausmuzsmausni f ausupm½W	«csp^80?81» yct;yg#d[m&d ausupm	&mr m"ywd("r&pw) rifBubonf yg#d[m&d apwUw&wn&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupmjzpf onf	yct;N~W a&f&Bub&m; ausmuzsm ausni f ta&Bbuf yg#d[m&d apw&t aemuf bufr&ipaw&
7	yct;N~W a&f&Bub&m; ta&B&ausupm½W	«csp^77» yct; ou&f;wef ausupm	&mr m"ywd("r&pw) rifBubonf ou&f;wefapwUw&wn&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupmjzpfonf	a&f&Bub&m; ta&B&ausuf pm½&t a&B buft&ü pwi&aw&&
8	yct;N~W a&f&Bub&m;/ ausmuzsmausni f? ta&Bbuf yg#d[m&d apw& taemuf bufr&ipaw& (rv&ae&m)	«csp^80?81» yct;yg#d[m&d ausupm	&mr m"ywd("r&pw) rifBubonf yg#d[m&d apwUw&wn&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupmjzpfonf	
9	yct;N~W a&f&Bub&m;Oif? tw&f;?taemuf awmi&xmi h ausupm½W	«csp^82» yct;?r [maAm"d ausupm	&mr m"ywd("r&pw) rifBubonf t*ü&aAm"yifpU&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupmjzpfonf	
10	yct;N~W/a&f&Bub&m; te& Oyuorm*r apw&(rv&ae&m)	«csp^76» yct; Oyuorm*r apw&usupm	&mr m"ywd("r&pw) rifBubonf Oyuorm*r apwUw&wn&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupmjzpf onf	
11	yct;N~W ustuy&f&b&m; (rv&ae&m)	«csp^68» yct; ustuy&f&b&m; ausupm	[kbmOw&y&n&mr m"ywd ("r&pw)rifBubonf ustuy&f ½&yf&f&av;qu&Uw&wn&Mumi f a&;x x m;aom ausupm jzpfonf	

pOf	, aeIvnae&m	rēāusnuḫpm aygi f, cšyřřn azmfytrnf	tallumi f, t&mt cšyř	ršvtsuf
12	yčt, NřV / rḫvĒm tĥ ? t a&āwmi āxmi h (rIvae&m)	«cspř 75» yčt? rḫvĒm ausnuḫpm	&mr m''ywd ('rāpw) ri f, Buḫoni rḫvĒm apw uĥ wn āLumi f, a&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	
13	yčt, NřV / acgi faq; uřef, bĥ m; uřef, (rIvae&m)	«cspř 83?84» yčt, acgi faq; uřef, ausnuḫpm	qlawmi f, ES h Buřpm rsm; uĥ a&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	
14	yčt, NřV / rĥĥ f, Buḫ bĥ m; / (rIvae&m)	«cspř 89» yčt, rĥĥ f, Buḫ bĥ m;	jrwpř bĥ m; \ oĥ; awmř 'mwř 33 ql &mr na' ool a&mu &ĥ āLumi f, ES h i f, oĥ; awmř ''mwř wĥ uĥ Xmyem x m; cĥ om a&šapw āw m uĥ jyřy i āLumi f, a&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	
15	yčt, NřV / a&ā r m ā ''m bĥ m; uřef awmř / (rIvae&m)	«cspř 94» yčt, oĥ; awmř 'mwř oĥ q, bĥ q ausnuḫpm	jrwpř bĥ m; \ oĥ; awmř 'mwř 33 ql &mr na' ool a&mu &ĥ āLumi f, ES h i f, oĥ; awmř 'mwř wĥ uĥ Xmyem x m; cĥ om a&šapw awmř uĥ jyřy i āLumi f, a&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	
16	yčt, NřV / uv sm P ā usmi f, wĥ ā usnuḫpm / (rIvae&m)	«cspř -ryg» uv sm P rēāusnuḫpm	taomuri f, omoem Mun ĥ onup i rē wĥ f, Xmae uĥ omoem a&mu &ĥ myĥ omoem oep i ā&; t wĥ uĥ t yř myĥ & [eř wĥ oř jyř wĥ yĥ e&ol trwĥ uř oř j c ES h t & y uĥ & š ř i oř j y kum oř forkvion ĥ t āLumi f, t E p w ā&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	o&yř eř Oḫ v ā z O i f jy eř qĥ wn f, jz w b n / 1958 / jyn ā xmi p k , O ā us ř O e Bu ḫ X me? rē f, O ā us ř X me p w /
17	yčt, NřV / ausnuḫwĥ uef &ĥ (taemu) / &aoĥř V (rIvae&m)	«cspř 64» &aoĥř V ausnuḫpm	[ĥ m O w] y n f &mr m''ywd ('rāpw) ri f, Buḫoni r [m &mr O ĥ m & a usmi f awm Bu ḫ uĥ wn ā xmi ā w m ř āLumi f, a&; xĥ x m; aom ausnuḫpm jzḫon /	

pOf	, ae\wn&e&m	r&e&usupm aygi f c&yl r&h azmjytrni	t aLumi f t & m t c&yl f	r&svtsuf
18	yct;N&W/ ausu&w&h f u e f &h/v&u&fayg b&m;c&E&piq t e h/ (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^67» b&m;c&E&piq l ausu&w&h b u h/	b&i f b u h&S&f&apmy&E&h" r&apw d ri f b u h&w&h n i a&S&t c g u w&h ri f b u h& E&S&f r&h&m; r [m o l b ' m w n f x m; c h o m u&f a y g b&m; c&E&piq u h x y f h y i f q i h a L u m i f a&; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	
19	yct;N&W/ x e f a w m b u h&h/ a&f&h&x m q l a w m i f j y n h b&m;/ (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^85?86» yct;N&W/ x e f a w m b u h&h? a&f&h& m q l a w m i f j y n h b&m; a u s u p m	j r w p h b&m; \ o h; a w m f ' m v B 3 q l & m r n a ' o o l a & m u & h a L u m i f E&S&f i f o h; a w m f ' m v h v u h X m y e m x m; c h o m a & S a p w h a w m f u j y f y i h a L u m i f a &; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	
20	yct;N&W/ b&m; b u h&h/ b&m; b u h b&m; / (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^87» yct? b&m; b u h a u s u p m	j r w p h b&m; \ o h; a w m f ' m v B 3 q l & m r n a ' o o l a & m u & h a L u m i f E&S&f i f o h; a w m f ' m v h v u h X m y e m x m; c h o m a & S a p w h a w m f u h j y f y i h a L u m i f a &; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	
21	yct;N&W/ z a v ; & h / u&f u r a w m f b&m; / (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^95» yct? z a v ; & h u&f u r a u m f b&m; a u s u p m /	j r w p h b&m; \ o h; a w m f ' m v B 3 q l & m r n a ' o o l a & m u & h a L u m i f E&S&f i f o h; a w m f ' m v h v u h X m y e m x m; c h o m a & S a p w h a w m f u h j y f y i h a L u m i f a &; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	
22	yct; c&h / v u o n h l e , / j r i f r i h&h / " r o l u b&m; / (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^88» yct; " r o l u b&m; a u s u p m /	j r w p h b&m; \ o h; a w m f ' m v B 3 q l & m r n a ' o o l a & m u & h a L u m i f E&S&f i f o h; a w m f ' m v h v u h X m y e m x m; c h o m a & S a p w h a w m f u h j y f y i h a L u m i f a &; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	
23	yct; c&h / v u o n h l e , / z t a c m i f & h / r h e u f b&m; / (r\vae&m)	«c&pf^90» yct? r h e u f b&m; a u s u p m	j r w p h b&m; \ o h; a w m f ' m v B 3 q l & m r n a ' o o l a & m u & h a L u m i f E&S&f i f o h; a w m f ' m v h v u h X m y e m x m; c h o m a & S a p w h a w m f u h j y f y i h a L u m i f a &; x h x m; a o m a u s u p m j z p l o n f /	

ပုံ(9) ယဇ်၊ ဘုရား၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ မြန်မာ၊ ရှေးဟောင်း၊ ရှေးဟောင်း၊ ရှေးဟောင်း

ပုံ(10) ယဇ်၊ ဘုရား၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ မြန်မာ၊ ရှေးဟောင်း၊ ရှေးဟောင်း

ပုံ(11) ယဇ်၊ ဘုရား၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ မြန်မာ၊ ရှေးဟောင်း၊ ရှေးဟောင်း

Z, မ(4)

ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်

ပုံ	အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	အင်္ဂလိပ်
1	ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	«ဇ(၇)» ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်	ရေဒီယို၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်၊ အင်္ဂလိပ်

pOf	, aeWnæ&m	rêausupm aygi fcsyrfn azmfytrnf	tallumi f t&mtcsyf	rsvtsuf
2	&efulef a&twf b&m; vrf oril f jywuluf	«csp ¹⁰⁶ » yct; a&armâ"m b&m; acgi favmi fpm		yct; rll&armâ" mapw& ifyi fS t* fvyf-jrefm ' kvd ppyf umv twlf tEd ol aqmi f, bñ; jci f&i umv uwâr; rllolla& mu&ae&mrS jrefm Eli fi bl wptzef jyeVnf &&bn/ [kmOwd acw&ri f wll \aemuqll vu&m/

y(12)a&Gwf b&m; rêausupm (tv, ausupmwl)

yl(13)a&ãrnb"mb&m; r&eacgi favmi fpm

Z, m(5)
r&ejyné, ftw&f aw&aom [kbm0w&bcwf r&eausupmrsn

pOf	, ael wn&e&m	r&eausupm aygi f&c&yf&f azmfytrnf	t aLumi f&t&m t c&yf	r&svtsuf
1	ustura&m	«c.pf^62?63» ustura&m ausupmrsn;	b&i fbu&S&f pmyloniustura&mb&m; tm; ajrv&om t aLumi f&a&; x&lxm; aom ausupmrsn;jzpfon/	
2	ox&ll	«c.pf^91?92» ox&llauvmo ausupm	jrwp&f&b&m; \ o&f; awmf' mwf&33ql &mrna' ool&a&mu&Lumi f&ES h æ i f&f; awmf' mwf&w&ll&myemxm; ch&om a&Sapw&awmf&ll&jy&yi&Lumi f&a&; x&lxm; aom ausupmjzpfon/	
3	ox&ll	«c.pf^93» ox&ll o&f; awmf' mwf o&llq, b&llql ausupm	jrwp&f&b&m; \ o&f; awmf' mwf&33ql &mrna' ool&a&mu&Lumi f&ES h æ i f&f; awmf' mwf&w&ll&myemxm; ch&om a&Sapw&awmf&ll&jy&yi&Lumi f&a&; x&lxm; aom ausupmjzpfon/	
4	rkvir&ll jro&f&wef b&m; &i&fyi&awmf ajrm&ub&uf (rlvae&m)	«c.pf^96» rkvir? ust&uzsi&ful b&m; acgi&favmi&fpm	acgi&favmi&fwp&cl&ub&e&f&vly&v&S' gef aLumi f&a&; x&lxm; on/	

pOf	, aeY wnae&m	r&eausupm aygi f.c.sYrfrh azmfy trnf	tallumi f,t&mt cshy	rSvcsuf
4	armVrfrh ustubefvel apwLulef awmf (r/vae&m)	«csp ¹⁰⁰ » armVrfrh f ustubefvel apwLulef & acgi f avmi f pm	acgi f avmi f wpclube f vlyms' gef allumi fa& ; xllxm; onV	

ပုဂ္ဂိုလ်တို့ ပြုဆောင်ခဲ့သော ဘုရားတော်တို့
တို့၏စွမ်းကုသုဒ္ဓါပေးသော ဗေဒနာ၊ မှန်မိလင်လောင်းစာပိုဒ်
မော်လမြိုင်မြို့၊ ကျိုင်းသန်လန်စေတီရှိ မှန်မိလင်လောင်းစာပိုဒ်
သိင်္ဃာတော်မိလင်လောင်း
ထားစေသော မြန်မာ့ဘုရားရှိ မှန်မိလင်လောင်းစာပိုဒ်
သုတေသနပေးသော မိလင်လောင်း
ရှင်မုနိဘုရားရှိ သုတေသနပေးသော မိလင်လောင်းစာပိုဒ်
ရွှေလောင်းမှန်မိလင်လောင်းစာပိုဒ်

yl(14)r&eyne, ft w&faw&aom [bnDw&cw f&e acgi f avmi f pnrsm

Z, m(6)

{&nDw&w f t w&f aw&aom [bnDw&cw f r&eausupm rsm

pOf	, aeY wnae&m	r&eausupm aygi f.c.sYrfrh azmfy trnf	tallumi f,t&mt cshy	rSvcsuf
1	ylorfrh a&pu&awmf b&m; &y&awmf we&aqmit	«csp ¹⁰¹ » ylorfrh uebo hqi h ausu&awm tzhr&ausu&pm	'ge? olv? bnDemullrar lravsnh t m; xkvf oi tallumi f a& ; xllxm; aom ausu&pm jzpb onV	ylorfrh uebo hqi h a' gu&vwmp h& h O, smOf aw&& onV
2	ylorfrh uebo hqi h a' gu&vwmp h& h O, smOf	«csp ¹⁰² » ylorf uebo hqi h ausu&pm tyll f us& rsm;	apw&wpqlu&wn& tallumi f a& ; xllxm; onV	ylorfrh uebo hqi h a' gu&vwmp h& h O, smOf
3	ylorfa& rla m b&m; &i fyif ay: ta& h ajrmulbu f (r/vae&m)	«csp ¹⁰³ » ylorfrh a& rla m r&ausu&pm	b&m; t m; ajrES hule&v& aom tallumi fa& ; xllxm; aom ausu&pm jzpb onV	

pOf	, aeY wn&e&m	r&ausupm aygic&yf&in azmfytrni	tallumi f&t&mt&c&yf	rsv&tsuf
4	yborf&½&f tokw&tr&W 'uP&m&½&W ausmif&Oif orfulef (riva&e&m)	«csp&f104» yborf c&½&f tokw&tr&W&rs ausmupm	b&m&;u&y&yf&i f&ci f&ES&h&j&r&u&lef v&sj&ci f&t&allumi f&a&;x&W&x&m&; aomausmupmjz&p&on&/	

azmfyygZ, m&;r&sm&;t& tv, &acw&r&f&ep&[k r&sv&f, l&x&m&;a&om r&e&ausmupm&r&sm&;on&f
[l&bm&O&w&h&cw&f r&e&ausmupm&r&sm&;jz&p&ly&ð y&ct? &efulef uO? u&stura&m? ox&W r&kw&ir?
arm&v&r&h&f? y&borf? y&k&h&' or&sm&;w&of aw&B&y&gon&/ allu&;y&B&y&lu&w&p&f&q? acg&i f&av&mi f&p&m
(5)c&ES&h&u&se&fur&h&f&p&m&w&r&f&in& ausmupm&r&sm&;om&jz&p&allumi f& azmfy&E&h&ly&gon&/

[l&bm&O&w&h&cw&f&e&ausmupm&v&mt& allumi f&t& &mr&sn&a&v&lv&nc&suf

ausmupm&w&h& tallumi f&t& &mr&sm&;u&h&av&lv&ma&om&f a&&w&v&f& b&m&; a&em&u&cb&r&il& fy&gon&h&a&&w&v&f&h
ap&w&d&a&umi f&r&ausmupm&/ r [m&AR&O&i&f&ow&x&me tallumi f&t& &mw&ES&h&q&u&py&h&ea&om& ub&lv&f
a&umi f&rl& y&ð&b&m&*ap&w&lv&n&j&ci f&t&allumi f&t& &mr&sm&; a&;x&W&x&m&;on&h&ausmupm&r&sm&; / of&i&;a&w&mf
(33)q&l a&&mu&B&f&l tallumi f&ya&om& a&umi f&r&sv&lv&r&f&ausmupm&r&sm&;ES&h , i&f&w&h&S& ty&jz&p&om
t&j&cm&; tallumi f&t& &mr&sm&;u&h&a&;x&W&x&m&;a&om& ausmupm&r&sm&;u&lv&n&f& aw&E&h&ly&gon&/

]]a&&w&v&f&h&b&m&;ausmupm&}}on&f r [m&AR&O&i&ES&h& q&u&py&h&ea&om& tallumi f&t& &mr&sm&;
jz&p&ly&gon&/ a&*g&w&r&AR& b&m&;&S&f& b&m&;t&jz&p&lu&h& a&&mu&f&aw&m&r&ly&ð&a&em&uf& ow&x&m&ew&lv&w&of
o&lv&i&f&ol&h&ep&O&um&v& vi&f&v&f&fy&i&u& p&h&ea&w&m&r&cb&ef& ul&e&on&in&h&em&i&w&v&h& a&&mu&B&v&my&h
v&sz&G& f&sm&; q&u&f&uy&f& tv&S&ly&h& q&h&w&mf& c&sj&r&f&ly&h& o, &h&q&mi&f&v&ml&uy&h& a&&w&v&f&h&p&w&d
w&n&x&m&;u&h&u&G& fy&h&sm&;u&h& azmfy&x&m&;y&gon&/ x&h&em&uf& r&e&r&i&f&t&q&u&q&u&f& j&y&f&y&i&f&f&r&h
a&umi f&r&j&ly&ml&uy&h&sm&;ES&h "r&ap&w&v&ir&f&? a&umi f&r&j&y&K&x&m&;y&h&sm&;u&h& azmfya&;x&W&x&m&;a&om "r&ap&w&d
ri&f&\ a&umi f&r&sv&lv&r&f& ausmupmjz&p&ly&gon&/ p&ausmupm&on&i& ow&x&m&eta&llumi f&ES&h
q&u&py&h&ea&om& ausmupm [lv&n&f& r&sv&f, E&h&ly&gon&/

r [m&AR&O&i&f& tallumi f&t& &mw&ES&h& q&u&py&h&ea&om& ub&lv&f&a&umi f&rl& tallumi f&

r [m&AR&O&i&f& ow&x&m&eta&llumi f&t& &mw&ES&h& q&u&py&h&ea&om& ub&lv&f&a&umi f&rl& tallumi f&
t& &mr&sm&; a&;x&W&x&m&;on&h& ausmupm&r&sm&;w&of&]]t&Zyg&va&usmupm&}}v&n&f& w&p&ck&t&y&g&t&O&i&f
jz&p&ly&gon&/ t&Zyg&v& q&v&a&us&ni&f&an&mi&fy&i&on&i& ow&x&m&ew&lv&fy&g&O&i&h&tr&u& b&m&;y&G& &ef
t&w&lv&f& o&Z&mv&m& o&a&x&;or&ð& *E&B&E&h&q&f&f&q&u&f&uy&B&m& ae&&mv&n&f&jz&p&on&/ x&h&e&&m&\
j&r&i&r&w&h&u&h& tav&;t&j&r&w&fy&K& t&Zyg&v&ap&w&lv&h& w&n&j&ci f&jz&p&allumi f& a&umi f&r&f&t&v&sv&lv&r&f&
ausmupmjz&p&ly&gon&/

y&ct?]]oly&lv&v&ð& ap&w&h& ausmupm&r&f&in& b&m&;tav&mi&f& Cem&E&h&q&f&f& b&D&f&ay&aw&mf&r&j&ci&f&r&S
p&i& a&&E&lv&f&q&e&h&aw&m&r&j&ci&f&t&q&h& we&u&a&om&w&ac&sm&i&\ ae&&ñ&h&r&p&Dr&S& oly&lv&v&ð& q&ly&fol&

jyeáwmi rlonf t x d & ; x H x m ; Ny? a & \$ r i f w l o y l v d a p w d w n b o u b l w n h a l u m i f a & ; x H x m ; o n f

yct?] ' O g O d [m & a p w d] a u s u p m r f n b l & m ; t a v m i f a & t v i y e f a r o n y d ? o y l v d q d y r s w u i u m u l u h a w m i a e i ' O g O d [m & w l f p m e D i p m ; a e \ / u l u h y G t w h e k u i r t d u l l f w G f p l a o m a l l u m i h a & c d & e l w G f q i f u o t n ; a o m a e & m w G f a & \$ r i f w l a p w d w n b o u b l x H O g O d [m & a p w d w n h a l u m i f a & ; x H x m ; o n f

yct?]] b r h p u r a p w d] a u s u p m r f n j r w p t n b l & m ; o n f o y l v d q d y o l o n t r ; & m v r f u p b u e k u a e p O f a e & ñ r p l o n h a & B u d a o m v n f b l & m ; & S \ " k m e a l l u m i h p b u e k u & m a e & m a & r j r k y l & y E S h O 1 / 2 a O V u o y & a o h t h b & y h e & m u l l a & \$ r i f w l u x l u e f a j r \ t p e f E p l o u i w f b r h p u r a p w d w p q p d w n b o u b l w n h a l u m i f a z m f y x m ; o n f

yct; r H ?] j e [m e a p w d] a u s u p m r f n v n f r [m a A m ' y i & & m w G f j r w p t n b l & m ; a & o y t h , h a w m i r h a o m t & y u a & \$ r i f w l e [m e a p w d w n b x m ; o u b l w n b x m ; a l l u m i f a z m f y x m ; y g o n f

yct? b & m ; o h q & t n ?]] r p v E m] a u s u p m r f n t Z y g v a n m i y i f s c E p & u j y n f r p v E m t h f t a & h a w m i b o u r u s y i f n o l w i f o n i O r k w i b c c h m ; a e p O f r h & h a o m a l l u m i h r p v E m e * g ; r i f u r h v r x & e l u m u G f t y f h x m ; y E S h a & \$ r i f w l x l t & y u r p v E m a p w d w n b o u b l w n h a l u m i f a & ; x H x m ; a o m a u s u p m j z p y g o n f

yct?]] O y u o r m * r a p w d] a u s u p m o n f t Z y g v a n m i y i f s w & m ; O d a [m & e f E o y w e r t ' g o l e a w m o l t o t n ; * , m o b a w m i l u m ; w G f O y u t m Z O u w u i v e f E S h a w l r E p l o u i o t n ; y E S h x h a w m i l u m ; w G f a & \$ r i f w l O y u o r m * r a p w d w n b o u b l w n h a l u m i f a & ; x H x m ; y g o n f

yct;]] y g # d [m & d]] a u s u p m o n f b l & m ; j z p a w m r l y d y O O * l u l l w & m ; O d a [m & e f t Z y g v a n m i y i f s E o y w e a w m o l u o n r s O 1 / 2 a O V u o y & a o l u l a c c s R w y m t q i l q i h u l l a & ; o m ; x m ; y g o n f

yct?]] r [m a A m '] a u s u p m r f n r p t n ' d d i t w p f y g ; o n f r [m a A m ' y i f u l l z s u f q d a v o n f r a t m i j r i ? j r w a o m t & y f t j z p f q u i v u & s b e b o n f a " v r i f v n f w p z e f a A m ' y i f u l l z s u f q d j y e \ / e w t a y g i f w l t y i i , j z p a p i & s b e a p a o m v n f a " v r i f u c k v j z w f r d w l u i t b u r b u r t z s u f q o n f e w i w l u x l i f u l l y s u p b a p a o m a l l u m i h] t * h & a A m '] [k a c : w G f y h t x d a & ; x H y g & t n f

azmfyyg t a l l u m i f t & m w l b n f A R \ j z p a w m p O f s b & m ; t j z p f & a w m i j c i f r s o l C m . t z d t p n f a y : a y g u i v m o n f t x d t a l l u m i f t & m r s m ; j z p l y d ? y & d b m * a p w d w n b x m ; a o m t a l l u m i f t & m r s m ; j z p l y g o n f o w k m e E S h q u e G h a o m t a l l u m i f t & m r s m ; [k q e l l y g o n f x l t j y i f x h u s u p m t m ; v h u -

]] r a E n r f u l y e f w r m r o l l i q u y , f o m o e m r y w l u k o p f t a o m u " r & m w l w * [v = a & s b l e f u & l u u l e h a o m o m o e m a w m l u l l u n i n h a o m j r w E m l u u l e h a o m t a o m u " r & m z i t p & h o m r i f w l b n f [h o m p m o m ; a & ; x H x m ; r l u l a w l & y g o n f r z a ' w G f t a o m u r i f y l a o m a u m i f r l

apwlyxhms;uH &mrnwllfa' owG f &mrn"ywd "r@pwrifBudoni ybNvl
xywlylaumi frljyly&avonf

oH;awm(33)ql wnxmaom ubN/haumi frit aLumi f

oH;awm(33)ql a&mu&fl taLumi fyaom aumi fhrSwlwr f, ausnupmrsm;uHvnf,
aw&ygonf jrwpbhb&m; y&eAhejylaomtcg awaZm"mwavmi fyD? oH;awmlyH;
oHq, h oHqluH o&Hmaomurif&&f ausnuapwH , f oHq, h oHql wnxm;uH uG f
clbnf t&S baomeax&ES h t&S Dw&ax&wH aysmuuG haom apwBhQ, h oHqluH
azmxkwy;í uH uG &aLumi f oxH oH;awm"mwf oHq, h oHql ausnupmwG f
azmfyxm;onf xHtaLumi f t&mutyif jrwpbhb&m; y&eAhejylaomtcg awaZm"mwf
avmi fyD? oH;awmlyH; oHq, h oHqluH o&Hmaomurif&&yluH tus, t&lum a&;om;
xm;lyD? o&Hmaomurif uH uG yHtaLumi f a&;xHxm;onfuH yct? oH;awm
"mwf oHq, h oHql ausnupmwG f aw&ygonf

azmfyygtaLumi f t&mrst uH yct;NHL? xefawmBud&H? a&Fh |mqawmi f jynh b&m;
ausnupm? yct;NHL? b&m;Bud ausnupm? yct;NHL? zav;&H? uHuraumf b&m; ausnupm/
uONHle, ? "r@Lub&m; ausnupm/ uONHle, ? rHeub&m; ausnupm/ oxH auvmo
ausnupm? oxH oH;awm"mwf oHq, h oHql ausnupmwG f aw&ygonf

r [mAR Oift aLumi f t&mES h oH;awm(33)ql taLumi f t&mwll [kw&om taLumi f t&mrsm

r [mAR Oift aLumi f t&mES h oH;awm(33)ql taLumi f t&mwll r [kw&om taLumi f t&m
rsm;rHn txuHwG hazmfyclonht wll f, r [mAR Oift aLumi f t&mES h oH;awm(33)ql taLumi f
t&mwll uH tm;jy&a&;om;jci fr [kw&om taLumi f t&mrsm;uH qlwlygonf

om" ut m;jzi h uvsmPbtf r&ausnupmwG f t"ut m;jzi h taomurif, omoem
Munhbnupí r&wll fXmaeuH omoem a&mu&vmyH &mrnwll fonf rHbaoma' o
jzpaLumi f? &mrnwll f wG f & [efawmllt wll f omoemht npft aLU; aq;allum&ef
oHfvt y&aLumi f? & [efwll oHfjykvlyyH omoemoepi&a&;twll f vHtyfmyH
xHtwll f oHfaqmuHlyf vl'gef&ef vHtyaomallumi H e&ol trw\ uGf;objcES h
t&yHl&S fí oHfjykm oHfokwlonht aLumi f tEpw&a&;xHxm;aom ausnupm
jzpygonf p wG hazmfyyg r [mAR Oift aLumi f t&mES h oH;awm(33)ql taLumi f t&mwll
ygOif r&Humi f aw&ygonf

yct ou&fwe f, ausnupmwG f [hbmOwlyjn&mrn"ywd ("r@pwr)rifBudoni
a&Stcgu wG rifBud\ r&H;r [mob' m wnxm;chaom b&m;(7)qluH xyHlyiqif
aLumi f a&;xHxm;aom ausnupmjzponf yct;b&m;cESql ausnupmi, f&vnf,
[hbmOwlyjnf &mrn"ywd("r@pwr)rifBudoni a&Stcgu wG rifBud\ r&H;r [m
ob' mwnxm;chaom b&m;(7)qluH xyHlyiqifaLumi f a&;xHxm;aomausnupm jzpyg
onf

yobHrH a&Lun&aemuHb&m; ausnupmwG fvnf apwlvpfqlwG f "mwawmLUkwf
ES haLU;qifwponf wll uH v'gef aLumi f a&;xHxm;aom aw&ygonf xHtwll yobHrH
uebHqih ausnubow&n tzHrausnupm? uebHqih ausnupm tyH f u&srsm;? yobHrH

p0f	acwf	ausmupmtrnf	ausmupmtu&myhumuEkvcsuf
5	[lbm0wd	&SfrxDb&m;&B o&d mulrm&f r&ef acgifavmi fpm (xm;0, trll)]]- [tryleerkaibqmya' gpbmoemrD-}

trsvp0(5) ylnf [lbm0wacwf [k qomlvnf, acgifavmi fpm jzpbnhitwuf ausmufx0f ravmuf vG fuhr&Eh f [k , kygon/ xltwuaMumi h tu&mtof rfn pmvWlyboft& aemuyh f usonf [k qEh faomlvnf? tajccWlyboft abmrn [lbm0wd acwf [ef ½neonf [k r&ef qEh fygon/ xMumi h [lbm0wacwf aEhif yhf, toG f [k r&ef qrygon/ [lbm0wacwft xd tu&moG jyi f xjcm; rfn ausmupm? acgifavmi fpm wlt & c&m; Oef, wpenf, tu&mtO h fpmvlyh to hraw&ao; aMumi f, azmfyEh fygon/

r&epmayta&;tomavlvnri

ta&;tom; avlvnrhtaajizih r&epmaytv, facwfac: [lbm0wacwf r&epmay a&;om;ri wGlvnf, pmayta&;tom;wlvn obm0twlf, r&epmaytohwGfus, haom umvjzpf pmayta&;tom;wlvnif a0a0qmqm &lygon/ om"utjzpf tZygv r&eausmupm wGf (u)rsuEh aMumi fa&(12-13)wGf

-]]x; axm&f raEh r f Awf ik, farG lvuf uomy* [f}}
- =wezh ai Gvpboef avmuf &h om a&Tvi f yef/
-]]pkwif jAyif jyaef tlvof h f wk f}}
- =t h x h s E h q h f, t m; v l u h x n h a v m i f, l y d a o m f
-]]e x; axm&f arG &m pi f} =tjcm; a&Tvi f yef, wptsyfzi h
-]]aj*myf jyrme f * [lvk f} =Eh q h f u h z h t h f l y d a o m f
-]]e, mwfr*lp; * [f lvk f} =jzlpifaom tjcm; tOwf jzi h xlyfy h l y d a o m f

[li a&;x h x m; r l u h a w l y g o n f¹² p a&; x h r w G f] r } } e m r O h o o e y k f a j y m i f y p o n t j z i h B u d m p u m; v h r s m; u h e m r O h o o e j y k u m v i f y e f E s h t O w l w l n * P & n l u h x i & n; a p l y f ?]] w k f * y l v k f } = l y d a o m f]] e } } = - j z i h [h o m r e O g u s q u ? r e f y k f q u f p u m; v h a v; r s m; j z i h O g u s h a o m l v n f ? t e u h a y s m u r o h; a t m i ? a O O g; r o h; a t m i f a O a O q m q m a &; o m E h h a M u m i f a w l y g o n f

uvsmP h r e a u s m u p m w G l v n f & m r n w l f \ r h a u m i f y l u h a &; x h x m; & m i t r e f & B r l u m r l u m & n w w l o v l q, & u f t x d h a p w w y l u h l v n f a &; x h x m; o n f p o n t u h O p v a z o i f, j y e q l v n i j z w o n h u v s m P h r e a u s m u p m p m t l y f p m r s u E h - 1 1

¹² oef, oefEG f 2012? 12/

]]apwq =apw0y&#? > apwq }}
]]vuéyabZmfcit^ewpwmwifci? > vu}}
]]jA [@ jrwbomtusi f jrwbomtusi luLusi fo> jA#}}
]&y=tqif > ½y}})

[lom pum;v#rsm;17 ponpum;v#wlonf ygVbuúv pum;v#wluú wlu½lufohyj
 r@wW\ pum;oES h &Gwq&vG lúap&ef rlvum;v#rsm;uú jyl/yifxm;aom pum;v#
 to#rsm;tjzpf aw&ygon/ r@bompum;twúf bmonjcm;pum;rs & Di&amuf
 ar±xm;aom ar±pum;v#rsm;yi f jzpfygon/

h# h#oytsuf

tv, ácwíwpenf [lom0wácw\ réausupmrsn;uú avh#maomaLumi h atmufig
 tcsufsm;uú aw&azmfyEúfygon/

- (1) [lom0wácwf réausupmrsn;onf rsm;aomt#jzih "rápw#if\ aumi#rl
 ausupmrsn;uú trsm;q#aw&ygon/ tv, ácwí#réausupmuú tvG f
 tm;jzihat' (1200-1500) [lí azmfyEúfygon/
- (2) ausupmw#wúf aw&aom talLumif;t&mv#r#n aumi#r#sv#vrf [k q#onf
 vnf aumi#rly&onh aemuch#talLumifum; taomurifup#k#i jyl#aom
 aumi#rl jzpaLumif;ES h Ar jzpa#wmpOES h qupy@aom talLumif#rsm;tav;uú
 azmfyxm;riúú aw&ygon/
- (3) uvsmP#ausupmubú onf jzpay:&ev#t#ytsufuú Ar #mayaemuf# a' o
 tajctaeaemuf#v#ES h#vuG azmfyxm;r#r#vnf aw&ygon/ x#Lumi h
 t, ácwíwpenf [lom0wácwí réausupmw#wú tajctaersn;uú oem;
 vn&ygon/
- (4) a&#répmayES h tv, ácwí#répmayw#wú tu&mol#yiftaetxm; jcm;em;rl
 uúvnf aw&ygon/ acwí#réfta&;tom;ubú c&mOef(tu&mpmv#úúf)rsn;
 to#rjyl@aom;alLumif aw&ygon/ ta&;tom;r#vnf y#ácwíubúyif
 a0a0qmqm a&;omr#r# aw&ygon/ c#m;csuf xif[y#paom ta&;tom;
 rsm;jzih tqif#ri@aom pmayy#P#éf jzpaLumif em;vn&ygon/ x#tcsuf
 rsm;onf a&#répmayES h tv, ácwí#répmayw#wú jcm;em;y#babmuú oem;
 vn#pEúfygon/
- (5) ygVbuúv yg0ifcifr#n acwly#p#may bompum;w#wú v#fr#rlw#p&yf
 jzpfly#? bompum;w#wú obm0yifzpbón/ x#bbm0t& tv, ácwí r@f
 pmaywúfygVdouúv pmv#rsm;uú wlu½lu&, l o#p#rsm;&#bubú#répum;oú
 ES h v#lúávsm#&#om toú fajymi#ar±r#jzih&, lxm;aom ygVbuúv pmv#
 rsm;uúvnf aw&ygon/

¹⁶ ci#pef0#? cE#r#yg? 101/
¹⁷ oef;oefEG # 2012? 47? 49/

(6) xltjyif rēlomom? pmayta&;tom; \ vŷa0qmrulijzpaom rēf toŷy
pum;vltwlt ta&;ygrulvnt; owjykrēllygon/ xltlumi f bmompum; \
vŷa0qmrwof toŷypum;vltm; jzpaom 0bwf ypnf? orēwlt u@
onlvnt; ta&;ygalumi f; awlt&&ygon/

[lī jzplygon/

edlt

tv, ācwlvpēnt [lbm0wācwlt rēāusupmrs;ull avlvmrbonf rvG fulvāy/
oi lūm;a&;Eš h oiāxmufjzpa&; t"luxm; aqmi ½ū&jci fā lūmi h tEpōlvāzmyēll frl
r&āy/ oŷom [lbm0wācwlt rēāusupmwlt a, bk s oabmvuPmrs; azmāxwv
ēll jci f? a&xltalumi f t&mwlt u@cfl pbnf;ēll jci f? pum;vltm;avlvmrts qulvuf
vlyēll frnh oawoers; twūf vrfprsm;&ēll jci f [bomtajtaers; zelwēll frā lūmi h
toiftwi hauseyrl &&ygon/ xltajctaeull tajcjyki qulvuavlvmrts;ullvnt;
aqmi &ūbfr;rnf jzplygon/ ausZtwi xltūbfr;vltūlvnt; ausZtwi &ygon/

usrfulpm&i f

cpōēf? 0b (wntjzwf bmojyēb)/ (1965)/ **rēāusupmaygi fcyf** &ēlēf
jynāxmi p̄k; 0āusrKme? a&sa [mi f;olawoexme/

armi fāmi āq̄b (2014)/ **jrpōmlt ayawmausni fausupm avmi butsuēh avlv m csul**
, 0āusrDebutXmeu &ēlēftrōm;jywltwv f jykvlyāom (6-4-2014) z&rwv f
zwlūm;aompvrf/

jr? 0b(olwytē)/ (1961)/ **a&sa [mi f jrefmt u&mpvrf/** &ēlēf jynāxmi p̄k;refm ēll fi hwmft p̄k;
yēlyā&;Eš h pma&;Bud mXme/

jrjrcw (2010)/ **a&sa [mi f]rēācgifavmi fpm} rS av;eutlfrmonh p̄lyēG p̄may taxmuf**
txmrs/ &ēlēf xēf;azmi h' ;&š f; bPpmaumirwpmay/

vāz0if? 0b(jyēqlvnt;jzwōb)/ (1958)/ **uvstP rēāusupm** &ēlēf jynāxmi p̄k; 0āusr
0ēbutXme? rēf, 0āusrKmeplw/

omjrwf 0b(olwytē)/ (2015)/ **rēf jrefmt u&morli f/** &ēlēf p̄wlt;ctōpmay/

oēfoēfEG l a' :/ (2012)/ ybt? **tZygvapwāusupmavlv mcsul** rēāv; butyfr;a&; pmtlywlv/

atmi jri 0b? a' gulvv/ (2016)/ **uūlvvef rēāusupmavlv mcsul** &ēlēf jrefmpm Xme?
&ēlēfwūbvl/

ausnupmri lūlyltm

oxltw a&pm&b&m; ausnupm/ltl [Nvmyāusupm}

oxltw a&pm&b&m; ausnupm/ltl [y@yāusupm}

jynltw a&qhāwmb&m; ausnupm/ltl [useppōmri faumi f rēāusupm}

jrjrcw;ltl ayawmausni fausupm ajrmulbutsuēh rēlomom